

RETRIEVAL AUGMENTED GENERATION AND SCIENTIFIC KNOWLEDGE GRAPHS TO SUPPORT SCIENTIFIC HYPOTHESES GENERATION

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Abstract

We propose to combine a Large Language Model (LLM) based conversational agent using Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) with methods from Literature-Based discovery (LBD) that rely on scientific knowledge graphs to create an LLM based research assistant. A LLM based conversational agent connected to a scientific knowledge graph using RAG can facilitate hypotheses generation by uncovering novel insights and connections across a variety of domains, thus aiding exploratory research. Furthermore, such a system could aid the research process by providing an explanation and answering questions about the relation between two research concepts that are not directly related, rather via intermediate concept relations extracted from multiple papers. However, challenges such as ensuring the accuracy of retrieved information and managing the complexity of scientific terminology must be addressed to fully harness RAG's potential in this domain. Our proposed approach promises to accelerate scientific research by supporting both the generation of new research hypotheses and the efficient review of existing knowledge, marking a significant step forward in LBD and therefore automated scientific discovery.

Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)

Large Language Models (LLM) pre-trained on a generation task, also known as generative pre-trained transformer (GPT) [1] models, are gaining in popularity due to the up-rising availability of GPT based conversational agents like Gemini [2], GPT-4 [3] or open source alternatives like Mixtral 8x7B [4]. However, GPT models face the major issue of generating incorrect or even false information, when asked about information not available during the training phase [5]. Therefore, RAG combines traditional information retrieval techniques, such as vector search, with GPT models to refine the text generation process [6]. Utilizing RAG, documents are indexed into a vector database via an embedding model for retrieval. This approach fetches relevant information from databases or document collections, using techniques like vector search to find documents that match a user's query [7]. The GPT model then uses these retrieved documents or segments alongside the user's query to generate text that is not only fluent but packed with accurate, relevant and recent information without the need of either a time- and cost-consuming pre-training or fine-tuning phase of the GPT model. RAG utilizes GPTs rather as an interface

to access a knowledge databases than to provide this information itself and finds its application in various domains including question answering, content generation, and the enhancement of conversational AI, utilizing a connected corpora [6]. It therefore also addresses the issue of inaccuracies or "hallucinations" in GPT models [5] and provides similarity scores for the relevance of retrieved documents to the query, allowing users to assess the relevance of the generated responses.

Literature-Based Discovery (LBD)

LBD is a strategic approach aimed at discovering latent connections and insights within scientific texts [8]. It begins with constructing a scientific knowledge graph from literature, identifying key concepts and their relations. For instance, one scientific paper might contain the relation that "fish oil" reduces "blood viscosity," while another contains the relation that high "blood viscosity" can be associated with "Raynaud's disease". This explicit knowledge might lead to the implicit hypothesis that fish oil potentially aids in the cure of the disease. Using this LBD approach this relation was hypothesized by Swanson and later proven to be correct [8]. LBD is currently used in the biomedical domain, due to existing knowledge graphs and ontologies like UMLS [9] enabling the identification of new drug targets and therapeutic approaches with systems like LION-LBD[10]. Recently, efforts have been made to utilize LLMs to construct scientific knowledge graphs in areas such as AI (AIKG) [11] and computer science (CSKG) [12], which might extend LBD applications beyond the biomedical domain. First experiments have also shown that link prediction on non domain specific (open-domain) scientific knowledge graphs might also be used to automatically create novel hypotheses [13].

Besides the automatic creation of novel hypotheses across research domains, LBD can assist research with open- or closed discovery. Open discovery begins with a search term and explores related concepts to forge new connections and therefore novel hypotheses. This approach does not only consider concepts directly related to the search term, and therefore extracted from scientific texts that mention the search term in combination with another concept, but also concepts extracted from scientific texts that do not mention the search term directly but are related to the search term via a related concept in the knowledge graph [8]. This might help to explore novel, potentially unexpected connections between concepts and aid in hypotheses generation.

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On the other hand, closed discovery starts with predefined hypotheses in form of the relation of two concepts. Paths between these two concepts from the scientific knowledge graph are returned to explore the literature across multiple scientific texts. These paths could be seen as either supporting or conflicting indicators for the given hypotheses.

Large Language Model (LLM) based Conversational Agent for Hypotheses Generation or Verification

The development of a conversational agent utilizing LLMs with RAG to support research through hypotheses generation or verification necessitates the integration of methodologies capable of mapping user queries to corresponding concepts within a scientific knowledge graph. Techniques such as keyword search [14], wikification [15], and taxonomy tagging [16] could complement RAG's vector search [7] to align user queries with relevant concepts in a scientific knowledge graph. Another approach could be to map the user query to a corresponding concept in the scientific knowledge graph is to unify the embedding of a text with the corresponding graph relation [17]. LLMs can also transform concept relations into narrative text [18]. When combined with user queries in a RAG-like fashion this approach could aid in hypothesis generation in the case of open-discovery LBD or verification in the case of closed-discovery LBD. Such a system could provide not only the generated responses but also quantify the similarity between the user's query and the identified relationships, along with the relevant scientific texts underlying these connections. Additionally, language models' reasoning capabilities, illustrated in the Chain of Thought (CoT) method [19], could be employed to verify or confirm relations for hypotheses generation. Ultimately, a LLM based conversational agent that integrates scientific knowledge graphs with RAG could serve as a valuable research assistant that helps facilitating LBD across multiple domains and make a step towards automated scientific discovery.

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